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ANNOTATION

Almost 75-80% of patients with ischemic stroke have headaches. Headaches are more common in young people than in middle-aged and elderly patients. It depends on the localization and mechanism of development of the source of ischemia and has a different nature, that is, intensity and duration. This is more common in patients who have previously suffered from migraines and severe headaches. According to some studies, headaches in patients with cardiovascular diseases are not associated with hypertension, and blood pressure is 120/80 mm. In the Hg state, son is often observed below. An increase in blood pressure reduces its intensity.

Key words: ischemic stroke, headache, migraine, headache strain

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ТЕЧЕНИЕ ГОЛОВНОЙ БОЛИ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ИШЕМИЧЕСКИМ ИНСУЛЬТОМ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Почти у 75-80% пациентов с ишемическим инсультом наблюдаются головные боли. Головные боли чаще наблюдаются у молодых людей, чем у пациентов среднего и пожилого возраста. Это зависит от локализации и механизма развития источника ишемии и имеет разную природу, то есть интенсивность и длительность. Это чаще встречается у пациентов, которые ранее страдали мигренью и сильными головными болями. Согласно некоторым исследованиям, головные боли у пациентов с сердечно-сосудистыми заболеваниями не связаны с артериальной гипертензией, а артериальное давление составляет 120/80 мм. В состоянии ниже Hg часто наблюдается нам. Повышение артериального давления снижает его интенсивность.

Ключевые слова: ишемический инсульт, головная боль, мигрень, напряжение головной боли

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ISHEMIK INSULT BILAN OG'RIGAN BEMORLARDA BOSH OG'RIG'INING KECHISHI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ishemik insult bilan kasallangan bemorlarning deyarli 75-80% gacha bo'lgan bemorlarda bosh og'rig'i kuzatiladi. Bosh og'rig'i o'rta va keksa yoshdagi bemorlarga qaraganda yoshlarda ko'proq kuzatiladi. Bu ishemiya manbaasining lokalizatsiyasi va rivojlanish mexanizmiga bog'liq bo'lib, boshqacha tabiatga ya'ni intensivlik va davomiylikka ega. Avval migren va kuchli bosh og'rig'idan aziyat chekkan bemorlarda ko'proq uchraydi. Ba'zi tadqiqotlarga qaraganda, yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari bilan kasallangan bemorlarda bosh og'rig'i arterial gipertenziya bilan bog'liq emas va qon bosimi 120/80 mm.Hg dan past bo'lgan holatda xam tez-tez kuzatiladi. Qon bosimining ortishi uning intensivligini pasaytiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ishemik insult, bosh og'rig'i, migren, bosh og'rig'i kuchlanish intensivligi.

Kirish: Ishemik insultdan keyin kelib chiqadigan bosh og'riqlarini erta aniqlash va oldini olishni o'rganish

Tadqiqot usullari. Ishemik insultdan keyin kelib chiqadigan bosh og'riqlarini tahlil qilish

Tadqiqot natijalari. Qon tomir kasalliklarini tashxislash va davolash klinik nevrologiyada dolzarb muammolardan biri bo'lib kelmoqda. Mamlakatimizda insult umumiy o'lim ko'rsatkichi bo'yicha yurak-qon tomir kasalliklaridan so'ng 2-3-o'rinda turadi. Ishemik va gemoragik insultning chastotasi mos ravishda 85% ga 15% ni tashkil etadi. Ishemik insult o'rta va keksa yoshdagi bemorlar orasida doimiy nogironlikning asosiy sababi bo'lib, birinchi oyda uning o'lim darajasi 30% ni tashkil etadi. Insult demensiyaning ikkinchi eng kech tarqalgan sababidir. Ishemik insultni imkon qadar erta tashxislash va ishemik insultdan so'ng saqlanib qoladigan qoldiq organik o'zgarishlarni kamaytirish. Insult tufayli yuzaga keladigan og'ir xolatlar va o'lim xolatini imkon qadar kamaytirish. Ishemik insultda bosh og'rig'ining tarqalishi olimlarning fikriga ko'ra turli xil intensivlikka 7-60% gacha tarqaladi. Hozirgacha ishemik insult bilan kasallangan bemorlarning ba'zilarida kuchli bosh og'rig'i qolganlarida esa pastroq intensivlikka ega yoki umuman bosh og'rig'i kuzatilmaslgi sababli aniq bir fikrlar yo'q. Shuni ta'kidlash joizki, o'choqli nevrologik yetishmovchilik (qo'l-oyoqning parezlari, nutq buzilishi, kordinatsiyaning buzilishi va boshqalar) bo'lsa bosh og'rigi ko'pincha e'tiborga olinmaydi, ayniqsa ong, afaziya va sezgi buzilishi mavjud bo'lgan bemorlarda. Bu nima degani? Bu o'tkinchi ishemik xuruj vaqtida, nevrologik buzilishlarning juda tez regressga uchrashi natijasida, ishemik insultdagiga nisbatan kuchliroq bosh og'rig'i kuzatiladi.

Ishemiya va bosh og'rig'i lokalizatsiyasi. Ko'pgina tadqiqotlar ishemik maydon va bosh og'rig'i bog'liqligini ko'rsatdi. S.M.Fisher va boshqalar, ichki uyqu arteriyasi trombozi holatining 31% da, o'rta miya arteriyasi trombozi va emboliasining 21% da, vertebrobasillar tizim trombozining 44% da, orqa miya arteriyasi trombozining 50% da bosh og'rig'i kuzatilgan. D.Uilyams va uning sheriklari tomonidan uyqu arteriyasi havzasida serebrovaskulyar zararlanish bilan bog'liq bemorlarning 25% da va vertebrobasilyar tizim zararlanishida 33% hollarda bosh og'rig'i kuzatilgan. Oxirgi o'tqzilgan tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, vertebrobasilyar soha ishemiyasida bosh og'rig'i chastotasi 15-65%, uyqu arteriyasi sohasi ishemiyasida esa 8-46% ni tashkil etadi. Shunday qilib, ishemiya o'chog'i vertebrobasilyar sohada joylashsa bosh og'rig'i kuchliroq asosan miyacha infarktida. Hozirga qadar buning sababi mavxum bo'lib qolmoqda. Ichki uyqu arteriyasi va o'rta miya arteriyasida zararlanish tufayli bosh og'rig' qoida tariqasida peshona-ko'z kosasi yoki teppa-chakka sohasida, ensa-bo'yin va quloqorti sohasida lokalizatsiyalanadi. Ba'zi xorij olimlari izlanishlariga

ko'ra vertebrobasolyar tizimdagi infarktda 50% xollarda bosh og'rigi peshona-ko'z kosasi sohasida qayd etiladi.

Bosh og'rig'ining uchrash koeffitsiyenti

Bosh og'rig'i va ishemik insultning patogenetik tipi

Avvallari bosh og'rig'i kardioenbolik insult bilan sezilarli darajada tez-tez sodir bo'ladi deb ishonilgan, ammo so'nggi tadqiqotlar bosh og'rig'i kardioenbolik ishemik insultga bog'liq emasligini aniq ko'rsatdi. Shunday qilib bosh og'rig'i kardioenbolik insult bilan 39% xollarda, aterotrombotik insult bilan 41% xollarda kuzatiladi. Lakunar insult bosh og'rig'ining salbiy prognozidir. lakunar insultda bosh og'rig'i tezligi 3-10% ni tashkil etadi va ko'pincha alohida sezuvchanlik kasalliklarida(<<sof sensorli>>insult) kuzatiladi. Bundan tashqari u ko'pincha vertebrobasilyar mintaqa isnuti paytida paydo bo'ladi, ehtimol bu o'sha xududning trigeminovaskulyar innervatsiyasi tufayli.

Bosh og'rig'i va ishemik hudud kattaligi. Bir qator xorijiy davlatlar tadqiqotlar ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, bosh og'rig'i intensivligi ishemik zona hajmiga bog'liq emas. Ko'pincha og'riq ikki tomonlama(61%)ayniqsa vertebrobasillar mintaqada qon aylanishi yomonligi,39% xollarda u bir tomonlama odatda miya infarkti tomonda kuzatiladi.

Bosh og'rig'ining boshlanish vaqti. Bosh og'rig'i insultdan avval,insult vaqtida yoki insultdan so'ng paydo bo'lishi mumkin.Bir tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatdiki bemorlarning 60% bosh og'rig'i insultdan avval,25% insult vaqtida,qolganlarda esa insultdan so'ng paydo bo'lgan.Bir necha soat yoki kun davomida bosh og'rig'i kardioenbolik insultda paydo bo'ladi.

Bosh og'rig'ining xususiyatlari

Nospetsifik xarakterli ishemik insultli bemorlarning ko'pchiligida bosh og'rig'i o'rtacha yoki yuqori intensivlikda bo'ladi. Ko'pgina xollarda bemorlar uni to'mtoq (35%), bosuvchi (31%) yoki o'tkir (20%) deb tariflaydi. Kamroq pulslı (8%)va kuydiruvchi (4%) deb ta'riflaydi. Ko'pincha o'z xususiyatiga ko'ra, ko'ngil aynishi, qusish, fono va fotofobiya birga bo'lsa kuchlanishli bosh og'rig'i (43-49%) yoki migren (28-42%) hurujiga o'xshash. Bosh og'rig'i bosh holatidagi o'zgarishlar, yo'tal va chakka arteriyasi siqilishi bilan kuchayishi mumkin.Og'riq intensivligi 1-kuni sezilarli yuqori bo'ladi va keyinchalik kamayadi. Bosh og'rig'i odatda insult vaqtida kelib chiqsa kuchli bo'ladi. Ishemik insultdan kelib chiqqan bosh og'rig'i odatda 1 kundan ortiq davom etadi, unung davomiyligi o'rtacha 3-4 kun. Lakunar insultda og'riq o'rtacha 19,5 soat davom etadi.

Ko'pgina tadqiqotlarda bosh og'rig'i yosh bolalarda o'rta va keksa yoshli bemorlarga qaraganda chastotasi kuchliroq kuzatiladi.Shunday qilib 40 yoshgacha bo'lgan yosh guruhida bosh og'rig'i 53% xollarda, 40-49 yoshda 32% xollarda, 50-59 yoshda 29% xollarda, 60-69 yoshda 27% xollarda,70 yoshda 24% xollarda,79 va 80 yoshdan oshganlarda 20% xollarda kuzatiladi.Shu bilan birga yosh va o'rta yosh bemorlarda vrtebrobasillar havza insulti vaqtida bosh og'rig'i kuchayadi.

Insult vaqtida birlamchi bosh og'rig'i

Avval serebrovaskular kasalliklar bilan kasallangan bemorlarda bosh og'rig'i kuzatiladi.Insult vaqtida stresli vaziyat bosh og'rig'ining asosiy sababi bo'lishi mumkin.Ishemik insult bilan kasallangan bemorlarning 43% da kuchlanish tipidagi bosh og'rig'i 15% da esa migren xurujiga o'xshash bosh og'rig'i kuzatiladi. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, ishemik insult bilan bosh og'rig'i avval migren bilan kasallangan bemorlarda ko'proq uchraydi. Bir tadqiqotda ishemik insult bosh og'rig'iga ko'ra taxlil qilingan. Unga ko'ra:

- *Migren bilan kasallangan bemorlarda migren bilan kasallanmagan bemorlarga qaraganda bosh og'rig'ining intensivligi yuqori.
- Anamnezida migren bo'lgan bemorlarda bosh og'rig'i ko'pincha migren xurujiga o'xshash.
- Migren bilan kasallanmagan bemorlarda bosh og'rig'i ko'pincha kuchlanishli bosh og'rig'iga o'xshash.
- Miya ustunidagi insult ko'pincha anamnezida migren bo'lgan bemorlarda paydo bo'ladi.
- Anamnezida migren bo'lgan bemorlarning 80% da bosh og'rig'i insultdan 24 soat avval paydo boladi.

- Miya stvolidagi insult bilan kasallangan bemorlarning 66% da insultdan avval migrenga o'xshash og'riq kuzatiladi.

Migren va simptomsiz miya insulti

Simptomsiz insult 8% bemorlarda uchraydi. Ko'pincha simptomsiz insult vertebrobasillar xavzada, ayniqsa miyyacha va miya yarimsharlari dorsal oq moddasida uchraydi. Bemorlar asosan migren xurujidan azob chekishadi. Bir oyda bir va undan ko'p migren xuruji kuzatiladigan migrenli bemorlar migren bilan kasaallanmagan bemorlardan 17.8 barobar ko'p. Simptomsiz infarktning mavjudligi ishemik insult xavfini oshiradi. Qizig'I shundaki, avval migren bilan kasallangan bemorlar ishemik insult bilan yengil kasallangan. Bu ma'lumot AQSH da o'tqazilgan keng ko'lamli ko'p markazli tadqiqot davomida aniqlangan. Bu tadqiqotda 37500 dan ortiq bemorlar ishtirok etdi va 7 ballik Rankin shkalasi bilan bemorlardagi nogironlik baxolandi. Bunda avval migren bilan kasallangan bemorlarda nevrologik o'zgarishlar migren bilan og'rimagan be'morlardan sezilarli darajada kam ekanligi aniqlangan. Bu migren bilan og'riq bemorlarda miya qon tomirlarining (lakunar infarkt) bilan tez-tez ishtirok etishi bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin.

Surunkali bosh og'rig'i bo'lgan bemorlarda ishemik insult xavfi

Surunkali bosh og'rig'i ayniqsa erkaklarda ishemik insultga shubhadir. Ushbu ma'lumot ishemik insult bilan kasallangan 45000 bemorda o'rganilgan. Surunkali bosh og'rig'i bo'lgan bemorlarda ishemik insult xavfi bosh og'rig'i bo'lmagan bemorlarga qaraganda 4 marta ko'proqdir. Bu bemorlar asosan 25-50 yosh oralig'idagi tez-tez chekuvchi va tana massa indeksi yuqori bo'lgan bemorlardir. Lekin haligacha surunkali bosh og'rig'i va insult o'rtasidagi patofiziologik bog'liqlik mavxumligicha qolmoqda. Tadqiqotlarga ko'ra ishemik insult va chekish o'rtasida bog'liqlik yo'q. Lekin bir qator tadqiqotlar surunkali bosh og'rig'i chekuvchi be'morlarda chekmaydigan bemorlarga qaraganda 10 baravar ko'proq kuzatilgan. Ishemik insult boshlanishida bosh og'rigi progressiv va asoratli o'zgarishlarda sezgining zararlanishini 56% ga, spetsifik o'zgarishlarni 99% va ijobiy tiklanish taxminini 98% ga oshiradi. Bu ma'lumotni ishemik insultdan tuzalayotgan bemorlarda orqa miya suyuqligidagi glutamat, interleykin-6, metabolit azot oksidi konsentratsiyasining ortishi tushuntirishi mumkin. Xuddi shunday xolat ishemik insult boshlanishidan avval bosh og'rig'i kuzatilgan bemorlarda ham uchraydi. Shunday tadqiqotlardan so'ng olimlar bosh og'rig'i ishemik insultning yaxshi prognozi ekan degan xulosaga keldilar.

Insult bilan kasallangan bemorlarda arterial qon bosimi

Tadqiqotlarga qaraganda bosh og'rig'i arterial qon bosimiga bog'liq emas va arterial qon bosimi 120/80 mmHg.ust bo'lgan bemorlarga nisbatdan arterial qon bosimi 110/70 mmHg.ust bo'lgan bemorlarda bosh og'rig'i ko'proq uchraydi. Qon bosimi oshgan bemorlarda arterial qon bosimini tushirishga qaratilgan choralar bosh og'rig'ini kamaytirmaydi. Bundan tashqari bosh og'rig'i qon bosimi tushgan bemorlarda intnsivligi sezilarli baland bo'ladi.

Xulosa: Ishemik insult bilan kasallangan bemorlarning bosh og'rig'i intensivligi erta aniqlash va oldini olish juda muhimdir. Maqolamozda keltirib o'tilgan kasalliklarda insultdan keying bosh og'rig'ini erta aniqlash ijobiy natijalarni beradi.

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